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TEXT MINING: OPEN SOURCE TOKENIZATION TOOLS – AN ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Text mining is the process of extracting interesting and non-trivial knowledge or information from unstructured text data. Text mining is the multidisciplinary field which draws on data mining, machine learning, information retrieval, computational linguistics and statistics. Important text mining processes are information extraction, information retrieval, natural language processing, text classification, content analysis and text clustering. All these processes are required to complete the preprocessing step before doing their intended task. Pre-processing significantly reduces the size of the input text documents and the actions involved in this step are sentence boundary determination, natural language specific stop-word elimination, tokenization and stemming. Among this, the most essential and important action is the tokenization. Tokenization helps to divide the textual information into individual words. For performing tokenization process, there are many open source tools are available. The main objective of this work is to analyze the performance of the seven open source tokenization tools. For this comparative analysis, we have taken Nlpdotnet Tokenizer, Mila Tokenizer, NLTK Word Tokenize, TextBlob Word Tokenize, MBSP Word Tokenize, Pattern Word Tokenize and Word Tokenization with Python NLTK. Based on the results, we observed that the Nlpdotnet Tokenizer tool performance is better than other tools.

KEYWORDS:

Text Mining, Preprocessing, Tokenization, machine learning, NLP

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A NEW DECISION TREE METHOD FOR DATA MINING IN MEDICINE

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ABSTRACT

Today, enormous amount of data is collected in medical databases. These databases may contain valuable information encapsulated in nontrivial relationships among symptoms and diagnoses. Extracting such dependencies from historical data is much easier to done by using medical systems. Such knowledge can be used in future medical decision making. In this paper, a new algorithm based on C4.5 to mine data for medicine applications proposed and then it is evaluated against two datasets and C4.5 algorithm in terms of accuracy.

KEYWORDS

Data mining, Medicine, Classification, Decision Tree, ID3, C4.5

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FUZZY-BASED MULTIPLE PATH SELECTION METHOD FOR IMPROVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN BANDWIDTH-EFFICIENT COOPERATIVE AUTHENTICATIONS OF WSNS

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ABSTRACT

In wireless sensor networks, adversaries can easily compromise sensors because the sensor resources are limited. The compromised nodes can inject false data into the network injecting false data attacks. The injecting false data attack has the goal of consuming unnecessary energy in en-route nodes and causing false alarms in a sink. A bandwidth-efficient cooperative authentication scheme detects this attack based on the random graph characteristics of sensor node deployment and a cooperative bit-compressed authentication technique. Although this scheme maintains a high filtering probability and high reliability in the sensor network, it wastes energy in en-route nodes due to a multireport solution. In this paper, our proposed method effectively selects a number of multireports based on the fuzzy rule-based system. We evaluated the performance in terms of the security level and energy savings in the presence of the injecting false data attacks. The experimental results indicate that the proposed method improves the energy efficiency up to 10% while maintaining the same security level as compared to the existing scheme.

KEYWORDS

Wireless sensor network, Network security, bandwidth-efficient cooperative authentication scheme, fuzzy logic

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